

INTRODUCTION

Monetary policy is a set of actions the Central Bank applies to control, monitor and direct the money supply to serve and achieve specific ultimate goals by influencing macroeconomic variables (Omer, [1]). Barth [2] stated three main criteria for selecting ultimate goals: an ultimate goal should be measurable, subject to some degree of the central bank control variable, and have a predictable effect on economic performance. Ultimate goals have traditionally comprised full employment through getting a low unemployment rate or a high GDP growth rate, stability of the general price level through targeting a low level of the inflation rate, and exchange rate stability through pushing balance payments toward an appropriate position (Handa, [3]).

Monetary policy has instruments that enable it to influence ultimate goals. Usually, they can be divided into two categories: direct or indirect instruments. The first operates under the regulatory legal power granted to the central bank. The second type operates as a function of the central bank's ability to issue banknotes and the subsequent effect of changes in reserve money on financial markets, mainly money market conditions (Alexander, Balifto, and Enoch [4]).

Table 1

Monetary policy instruments and ultimate goals

Policy-instruments	Operating Goals	Intermediate Goals	Ultimate Goals
Open-market operations Discount rate reserve requirements	Short-term interest rates Reserve aggregates (monetary base, reserve, non-borrowed reserves, etc.)	Monetary aggregates (M1, M2, etc.) Interest rates (short and long-term) Aggregate demand	Low unemployment rate Low inflation rate Financial market stability Exchange rates

Table 1 illustrates that the monetary policy may be expansionary to combat unemployment during a recession by increasing the money supply via open market operations, discount rates, and reserve requirements, or it may have deflationary aims to reduce inflation. As for intermediate targets (monetary aggregates; M1, M2, etc.), Balfoussia, Brissimis, and Delis [5] shed light on a new trend in economic policy – since the early 1990s, the importance of monetary aggregates has weakened in central bank practice as a result of a new empirical issue that is established from factors such as financial innovation, climate changes, currency substitution, different growths in individuals' income, and rapid accumulation of wealth over the world and its interrelation and impact on the international financial system.

Literary sources on monetary policy efficiency revealed differences across countries in the performance of monetary policy due to the discrepancy in political and economic situations, ultimate goals, and the regulations followed by central banks. Omer [6] examined the efficiency of the monetary policy implemented by the Central Bank of Sudan in 2000-2018. The study used monetization deepening criteria, including the M2 to GDP ratio, Circulation of Currency to GDP ratio, and Banking Deposits to GDP ratio. The study used monetization indicators as a function of per capita income, rate of return on investment deposits, banking awareness, and inflation. The results found that the monetary policy was ineffective due to increased inflation, decreased return on investment deposits, reduced banking awareness, and a fall in per capita income. In December 2021, the European Central Bank (ECB, [7]) reviewed its strategy regarding climate change and monetary policy in the euro area. The strategy shed light on the potential impact of climate change on the macroeconomic and financial markets. Moreover, several academics, writers, and advocacy groups such as Grauwe [8] and Schoenmaker [9] are pushing the Central Bank to implement policies that positively impact climate change by applying a green monetary policy leading to Central Bank Balance Sheets toward low-carbon sectors. Besides, corporate bonds should be exchanged for new green bonds. Al-Jasser and Banafe [10] discussed the instruments and procedures of the monetary policy implemented by the Saudi Arabian Monetary Agency (SAMA) as an agent of the government. The study found that SAMA has a variety of targets and instruments, including short-term interest rates, money supply growth rates, monetary aggregations, inflation, exchange rates, and other economic indicators. Choosing targets is complex and problematic because it is often hard to determine, control, and regulate whether changes are accomplished by monetary or fiscal policy. Khatat et al. [11] argued that inflation targeting is the optimum selected future way for Tunisia's monetary policy. The outcome of the analysis is that the current monetary targeting is ineffective because of the structure of reserve money and the higher volatility of the money multiplier, especially after 2010. Omer [12] tested through a simple regression model how the monetary policy affected HDI in Sudan in 1999-2018. The model results indicate that monetary policy in terms of inflation indirectly enhanced HDI through money supply increases. Kose et al. [13] presented an inclusive analysis of inflation expectations, emphasizing emerging markets and developing economies. The results reveal that long-term inflation expectations in developing economies are not as well anchored as those in advanced economies. Nevertheless, through monetary policy regimes that include high transparency of the central bank, inflation targeting, solid inter-trade integration, and a minimum level of public debt, the developing economies have more ability to anchor inflation expectations.

Since the early 2010, revolutions called the Arab Spring or Arab Spring Revolutions (ASRs) swept over Arab countries. The ASRs aim to improve the Arab economic position and raise the

standard of living for citizens. The most prominent feature left by the ASRs is that they renewed hope and confidence in the possibility of reforming the political and economic systems. Therefore, since 2011, the ASRs succeeded in changing the political and economic systems of some countries, including Tunisia in January 2011, Egypt in February 2011, Libya in October 2011, Yemen in December 2017, Algeria in March 2019, and Sudan in April 2019. This paper seeks to review and analyze the indicators of monetary policies in the Arab Spring Countries (ASCs) in 2010-2020, and to determine whether these policies achieved their ultimate national goals, hoping that the conclusions will help bridge the gap between academic research and policymakers' decisions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To assess the performance of the monetary policy in ASCs from the time of Arab Spring until the year 2020, the following criteria will be reviewed and analyzed:

Inflation rate, measured by the consumer price index (CPI). CPI measures the average change over time in the prices paid by urban consumers for a market basket of consumer goods and services. Inflation reflects the extent to which the general level of prices is stable [14].

Unemployment rate, reflecting inability of an economy to generate employment for those who are out of work even though they are available for jobs and actively seeking them [15].

Current account balance, comprising all transactions and significant classifications of goods and services, income, and current transfers other than those in financial and capital items, and reflecting the extent of external balance and the local currency's strength [16].

Real GDP growth, the outcome of the annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency; it reflects the overall performance of economic policies [17].

Government debt to GDP, consisting of all liabilities that require payment or payments of interest and/or principal by the debtor to the creditor at a date or dates in the future, including debt liabilities in the form of SDRs, currency, and deposits, debt securities, loans, insurance, pensions, standardized guarantee schemes, and other accounts payable [18].

Human development index (HDI), measuring average achievement in three key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living [19]. The optimum value of HDI is preferred to be > 0.5 and $\text{Max} = 1$ for the most developed countries.

Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, obtained by dividing GDP at current market prices by the population [20]. It reflects the extent to which the income of individuals in society has improved (by dividing GDP at current market prices by the population).

The study is based on annual secondary data covering 2010-2020, mainly gathered from the IMF's World Economic Outlook (WEO) Database, published reports, and previous studies concerning monetary policy. The selected period is based on an important political event in late 2010 in Arab countries: the Arab Spring Revolutions (ASRs). The selection of countries depended on those whose spring revolutions had succeeded in changing their political systems. These countries include Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, Yemen, Algeria, and Sudan.

RESULTS

Tables 2 to 8 review the performance of monetary policy indicators (inflation rates, current account balance, real GDP growth, public debt as a percentage of GDP, GDP per capita, unemployment rates, and human development index) in Arab Spring Countries from 2010 to 2020.

Table 2

Inflation rate by countries in 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	4.4	11.7	2.5	11.2	3.9	13.0	7.8
2011	3.2	11.1	15.9	19.5	4.5	18.1	12.1
2012	4.6	8.7	6.1	9.9	8.9	35.6	12.3
2013	5.3	6.9	2.6	11.0	3.3	36.5	10.9
2014	4.6	10.1	2.4	8.2	2.9	36.9	10.6
2015	4.4	11.0	14.8	22.0	4.8	16.9	12.3
2016	3.6	10.2	24.0	21.3	6.4	17.8	13.9
2017	5.3	23.5	28.0	30.4	5.6	32.4	20.9
2018	7.3	20.9	-1.2	27.6	4.3	63.3	20.4
2019	6.7	13.9	4.6	10.0	2.0	51.0	14.7
2020	5.7	5.7	22.3	26.2	2.4	163.3	37.6

Source: IMF, [21]

Figure 1 and Table 2 illustrate the monetary policy performance of ASCs in terms of inflation in 2010-2020. Notably, except for Tunisia and Algeria, Arab Spring Countries reached approximately a double-digit inflation rate. Sudan is the higher inflation country among ASCs; its inflation rate ranged between 13% in 2013 and 163% in 2020. Egypt's inflation rate fluctuated between 5.7% in 2020 and 23.5% in 2017. Libya's inflation rate ranges from 2.5% in 2010 to 28.0% in 2020. Yemen's inflation rate ranged between

Figure1 Inflation rate trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 3

Current account balance by countries (in billion USD) in 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	-2.5	-4.3	14.6	-1.1	12.2	-1.7	2.9
2011	-3.9	-6.1	3.2	-1.0	19.8	-2.7	1.6
2012	-4.1	-10.1	23.8	-0.6	12.3	-6.3	2.5
2013	-4.5	-6.4	0.0	-1.2	0.8	-5.8	-2.9
2014	-4.7	-2.7	-19.0	-0.3	-9.4	-3.5	-6.6
2015	-4.2	-12.1	-9.3	-2.6	-27.3	-5.5	-10.2
2016	-3.9	-19.8	-4.6	-0.9	-26.5	-4.2	-9.9
2017	-4.1	-14.4	2.4	0.0	-22.1	-4.6	-7.1
2018	-4.4	-6.0	0.7	-0.5	-16.7	-4.7	-5.3
2019	-3.3	-10.9	0.9	-0.9	-17.2	-5.2	-6.1
2020	-2.7	-11.2	-2.5	-0.5	-15.1	-6.0	-6.3

Source: IMF, [22].

Table 3 and Figure 2 show that, except for Libya and Algeria, all Arab Spring countries achieved a continuous deficit in their current account balance in 2010-2020, where the deficit ranged between 0.5 billion USD (achieved by Yemen in 2020) and 19.8 billion USD (achieved by Egypt in 2016). Notably, Libya and Algeria achieved a current account surplus between 0.8 billion USD achieved by Algeria in 2013 and 23.8 billion USD achieved by Libya in 2012. Moreover, all ASCs reached a current account deficit on average, fluctuating between 2.9 billion USD in 2013 and 10.2 billion USD in 2015.

Figure 2 Current account trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 4

Real GDP growth by countries in 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	3.5	5.1	3.2	7.7	3.6	3.9	4.5
2011	-1.9	1.8	-66.7	-12.7	2.9	-3.2	-13.3
2012	4.1	2.2	124.7	2.4	3.4	-17.0	19.9
2013	2.8	3.3	-36.8	4.8	2.8	2.0	-3.5
2014	2.9	2.9	-53.0	-0.2	3.8	4.7	-6.5
2015	1.2	4.4	-13.0	-28.0	3.7	1.9	-4.9
2016	1.2	4.3	-7.4	-9.4	3.2	3.5	-0.8
2017	1.9	4.1	64.0	-5.1	1.3	0.7	11.2
2018	2.7	5.3	17.0	0.8	1.2	-2.3	4.1
2019	1.0	5.6	13.2	2.1	0.8	-2.5	3.4
2020	-8.8	3.6	-59.7	-5.0	-6.0	-3.6	-13.3

Source: IMF, [23].

Table 4 and Figure 3 show that Egypt achieved a fluctuating positive growth rate in 2010-2020, ranging between 1.8% in 2011 and 5.6% in 2019. This was followed by Algeria, which achieved a declining positive growth rate in 2010-2019, ranging between 0.8% in 2019 and 3.8% in 2014, while 2020 achieved a negative growth rate of 6.0%. As for the rest of the countries, the real GDP growth ranged from 66.0% to 64.0%. Regarding real GDP growth, the overall performance of ASCs fluctuated from 13.0% to 19.9%.

Figure 3 Real GDP growth trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 5

Government debt to GDP by countries in 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	39.2	69.6	-	42.4	10.5	74.6	47.3
2011	43.1	72.8	-	45.7	9.3	78.1	49.8
2012	47.7	73.8	-	47.3	9.3	117.7	59.2
2013	46.8	84.0	-	48.2	7.6	105.8	58.5
2014	51.5	85.1	-	48.7	7.7	84.4	55.5
2015	55.4	88.3	-	57.0	8.7	93.2	60.5
2016	62.3	96.8	-	77.3	20.5	109.9	73.4
2017	70.9	103.0	-	77.4	26.8	152.9	86.2
2018	77.5	92.5	-	74.5	37.8	185.6	93.6
2019	71.8	84.2	-	76.5	45.8	200.3	95.7
2020	87.6	90.2	-	83.2	53.1	262.5	115.3

Source: IMF, [24].

Government debt as a percentage of the GDP refers to the extent of public debt aggravation due to the deficit experienced by the public budgets of countries when their public expenditures exceed public revenues.

Figure 4 Government debt to GDP trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 5 and Figure 4 indicate that the overall performance of all ASCs in terms of public debt was constantly worsening, as it rose from 47.3% in 2010 to 115.3% in 2020. Algeria's best performance was reached as its public debt ranged between 7 % to 54% as a share of GDP. Sudan was the worst in this indicator, as the public debt as a percentage of GDP ranged between 74% and 263%. As for the rest of the countries, except Libya in the group, their public debt as a share of GDP ranged between 39% and 91%.

Table 6

GDP per capita by countries (in USD) in 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	4140	2923	11417	1267	4481	1637	4310.8
2011	4257	3077	5402	1302	5454	2034	3587.7
2012	4138	3379	12684	1368	5576	1396	4756.8
2013	4199	3404	8282	1516	5477	1463	4056.8
2014	4274	3520	3876	1574	5466	1629	3389.8
2015	3830	3731	2723	1501	4153	1679	2936.2
2016	3666	3654	2907	1062	3919	1639	2807.8
2017	3436	2485	4685	892	4080	1173	2791.8
2018	3443	2577	6362	762	4119	855	3019.7
2019	3324	3057	6055	713	3940	777	2977.7
2020	3323	3587	3281	620	3263	775	2474.8

Source: IMF, [25].

Figure 5 GDP per capita trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 6 and Figure 5 specify that although Libya achieved the best indicator among the ASCs in terms of per capita GDP, it tended to decrease sharply from 11417 USD through the 2010-2020 period ending at 3281 US dollars in 2020. Tunisia and Algeria have almost similar performances. Their GDP per capita ranged from 3263 USD to 5576 USD. Then comes Egypt, whose GDP per capita has ranged between 2485 USD to 3731 USD. While GDP per capita sustained a decline in Sudan and Yemen, where it fluctuated between 2034 USD dollars and 620 USD. The overall performance of ASCs, regarding GDP per capita, fluctuates between 2474.8 USD and 4756.8 USD.

Table 7

Unemployment rate by countries in 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	13.0	9.2	19.3	12.8	10.0	13.7	13
2011	18.9	10.4	19.4	13.2	10.0	12.0	13.9
2012	16.7	12.4	19.0	13.2	11.0	14.8	14.5
2013	15.3	13.0	19.5	13.3	9.8	15.2	14.4
2014	15.0	13.4	19.5	13.5	10.6	19.8	15.3
2015	15.4	12.9	19.5	13.8	11.2	21.6	15.7
2016	15.5	12.7	19.5	13.4	10.5	20.6	15.4
2017	15.5	12.2	19.4	13.3	11.7	19.6	15.3
2018	15.5	10.9	19.5	13.1	11.7	19.5	15.0
2019	14.9	8.6	19.7	13.1	11.4	22.1	14.9
2020	-	8.3	20.1	13.4	14.2	26.8	16.6

Source: IMF, [26].

Figure 6 Unemployment rate trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 7 and Figure 6 show that ASCs reached a double-digit unemployment rate; their annual average unemployment rate ranged from 13% to 17%, indicating that the monetary policy was inappropriate. Libya and Sudan have reached the highest unemployment among ASCs, their unemployment rates between 12.0% and 26% from 2010 to 2020. Egypt has the lowest unemployment rate, fluctuating between 8% and 13.5%. Meanwhile, Tunisia, Yemen, and Algeria's unemployment rates fluctuate between 9.8% and 18.9%.

Table 8

HDI by countries 2010-2020

Year	Tunisia	Egypt	Libya	Yemen	Algeria	Sudan	Annual Average
2010	0.72	0.67	0.80	0.51	0.72	0.47	0.65
2011	0.72	0.67	0.76	0.50	0.73	0.47	0.64
2012	0.72	0.68	0.79	0.50	0.73	0.49	0.65
2013	0.72	0.68	0.76	0.51	0.73	0.49	0.65
2014	0.73	0.69	0.73	0.50	0.74	0.50	0.65
2015	0.73	0.69	0.70	0.48	0.74	0.50	0.64
2016	0.73	0.70	0.69	0.47	0.74	0.51	0.64
2017	0.73	0.70	0.71	0.47	0.75	0.51	0.65
2018	0.74	0.70	0.72	0.47	0.75	0.51	0.65
2019	0.74	0.71	0.72	0.47	0.75	0.51	0.65
2020	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Source: IMF, [27].

Figure 7 HDI Trends of Arab Spring Countries in 2010-2020

Table 8 and Figure 7 display that although Libya achieved the best HDI among ASCs, it tended to decrease slowly from 0.80 in 2010 to end at 0.72 in 2019, followed by Algeria and Tunisia, their HDI ranging between 0.72 and 0.75, which indicates that human development, healthy life, knowledge, and standard of living were relatively stable in 2010-2019. As for Egypt, its HDI improved gradually from 0.67 in 2010 to 0.71 in 2020. Sudan's HDI improved slowly from 0.47 in 2010 to 0.51 in 2019. Yemen's HDI tended to decline slowly from 0.51 in 2010 to 0.47 in 2019 indicating that human development and standard of living are on the way to getting worse.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this paper is to review and analyze the monetary policy performance indicators in the Arab Spring Countries (ASCs), including Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, Yemen, Algeria, and Sudan, in 2010-2020, and to answer the following question: Do monetary policies in those countries achieve the goals the Arab Spring Revolutions (ASRs) aspired for? These goals were as follows: to improve the economic and standard of living of citizens through achieving minimal inflation rate, increase real GDP growth, low unemployment rates, minimize Government debt, current account surplus, pushing up levels of GDP per capita, and best HDI.

The analysis revealed that, except for Tunisia and Algeria, ASCs achieved almost a double-digit inflation rate ranging between 13% in 2013 and 163%, indicating monetary policy ineffectiveness among ASCs. Similarly, the unemployment rate achieved nearly double-digit

among ASCs, ranging from 13% to 17%, indicating that monetary policy is also ineffective in targeting the one-digit unemployment rate.

The analysis found variation across the ASCs in real GDP growth. Except for Egypt, all countries' GDP growth oscillated between negative and positive values, which indicates the inability to maintain a certain pattern of monetary policy's impact on economic growth. As a result, the GDP per capita has declined, reaching 775 USD and 620 USD in 2020 for Sudan and Yemen, respectively.

Concerning the current account position of ASCs, it is noted that except for Libya and Algeria, the current account balance achieved a continuous deficit from 2010 to 2020, ranging between 0.5 billion USD and 19.8 billion USD. The continuous deficit of the current account balance explains the increasing trend of the public debt of ASCs, as it is noted that the government debt to GDP continues to rise, fluctuating sharply between 53.1% and 262.5% in 2020. Therefore, the monetary policy in this regard is ineffective. The HDI divided the ASCs into two groups. The first group includes countries where the HDI has significantly improved, ranging from 0.67 to 0.80, including Egypt, Algeria, Tunisia, and Libya. The second group includes countries where the HDI ranged between 0.47 and 0.51, including Sudan and Yemen. This indicates the need to follow monetary policies leading to improving and maintaining an HDI to be more than 0.50.

The study's key conclusion is that the monetary policies applied by ASCs were not able to achieve their ultimate goals due to the decline in their performance indicators from 2010 to 2020.

The study recommends that political systems in ASCs in general and monetary authorities (central banks) in particular pay more attention to achieving political stability to ensure better performance of monetary policy indicators in the future.

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